

SPECIFIC HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHY OF THE FACTORS OF INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE EAST

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Abstract. *This article describes how our ancestors laid the foundations and developed the foundations of modern science many centuries ago.*

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The President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, mentioned how important this issue is for the current stage of our nation's development, the fate and future of our country: "It is clear to all of us that Uzbekistan has rich mineral and natural resources, powerful economic and human potential. However, it is not for nothing that it was emphasized that our greatest wealth is the great intellectual and spiritual potential of our people.

From the oldest petroglyphs and inscriptions created by the thinking and genius of our ancestors, from examples of folk oral creativity, to the thousands and thousands of manuscripts kept in the treasury of our libraries today, they embody history, literature, art, politics, ethics, philosophy, medicine, precious works on mathematics, mineralogy, chemistry, astronomy, architecture, agriculture and other fields are our great spiritual wealth.

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Intellect (Latin intellectus "perception"; "comprehension", "comprehension"; "concept", "reason"[1]) or mind[2][3] is a quality of the psyche consisting of the ability to recognize new things. situations, the ability to learn and memorize through experience, to understand and apply abstract concepts, to use one's knowledge in managing the human environment[4]. The general ability to know and solve problems that combines cognitive abilities: perception, perception, memory, representation, thinking, imagination[5][6].

According to the theory of intelligence of psychologist Raymond Cattell [7], intelligence is conditionally divided into active and crystallized. The first is the ability to think logically, analyze and solve problems that go beyond previous experience; the second includes the ability to use accumulated experience and acquired knowledge and skills.

14 unique qualities of intellectual development factors:

In many sources, an intellectual is defined as a person who has the ability to acquire new knowledge and apply it in practice. This definition is very close to the meaning of wisdom, although they are very different from each other. Aql (mind, intellect) has a certain aspect of "learning", and a person shows superiority over other people in terms of understanding, creativity, self-knowledge, problem solving, and other qualities. If someone calls you smart or intelligent, they are assuming that your brain is more efficient than others.

Many people wonder what makes a person intellectual. Here it is important to understand that each of us has our own potential. The following are general qualities common to all intellectuals:

1. They understand limitations. If they don't know something, intellectuals are the first to be recognized. In comparison, their less intelligent opponents always try to avoid such admissions for fear of looking stupid. And only the first one understands that it is impossible to know everything about everything. If you are lucky, you can get valuable knowledge from everything. So if you ask a smart guy a question he doesn't have an answer to, you'll get an answer of "I don't know." But the probability that he will find an answer is very high.

2. They love to learn. Most people consider the famous founder of Apple, Steve Jobs, to be a brilliant mind. In any case, it revolutionized the field of personal computers. Steve loved to read, even though he once dropped out of college. He always told the junior staff that if they wanted to achieve something, they had to study even after classes were over. Jobs, like many other successful entrepreneurs, understood that learning is important. Even if it has nothing to do with the college curriculum.

Highly intelligent people know that only new knowledge leads to new ideas. They lead to a correct understanding of the world around them.

3. They are open-minded people. People with high intellectual development are more open to new ideas and ways of thinking. And because they put logic above all else, they are more objective and open in their judgments. Thus, intellectuals are less constrained in their views of social problems of racial, gender, or sexual inequality. They understand the biological and social nature of such problems while respecting human rights. Intellectuals are always open and willing to change their views because they do not follow their own ideas blindly or hear from someone. If you have a really great idea, they will listen to it, even if it goes against their own.

4. They have a great sense of humor. As a rule, intellectuals have a better sense of humor than other people. But sometimes their jokes do not elicit the expected reaction from those of average intelligence. Because "smart" people understand the world better and perceive social phenomena better, they can respond to jokes faster. As a personality trait, humor is inextricably linked with highly developed verbal communication skills. Therefore, it will not be difficult for an intellectual to laugh at those who initially rely on verbal communication and have a well-developed sense of humor.

5. They make mistakes and learn from them. It is easy to meet a person who has seen the consequences of mistakes made in the distant past. This may surprise you, but such an obsession with your failures shows a low level of intelligence. Intellectuals tend to make the most of their mistakes and move forward. Thomas Edison's teacher and thought he was too stupid to learn anything. But today we look at this man as one of the most talented inventors of the 19th century. He treated all his failures like this: "I didn't make two thousand mistakes in creating a light bulb. I discovered one thousand nine hundred and ninety-nine ways not to make a light bulb. Everyone knows the result - he succeeded.

6. They adapt easily. They say you can't teach an old dog new tricks. The same goes for people of "average" intelligence. To one degree or another, but all people must adhere to the moral standards established in society. However, this does not exclude attempts to find a way to make your life even better. Highly intellectually developed people adapt easily, succeed in any situation and in any environment. But most importantly, they succeed without compromising their

principles. The ability to adapt to any situation is a clear sign of high intelligence and success, regardless of any circumstances.

7. They like to solve problems. As NFL Hall of Fame coach Jimmy Johnson said, "Success comes when opportunity meets skill." This quote is so true that many successful people are literally living it without knowing it. Those who simply believe in luck and live in the hope that it will smile on them tomorrow will not achieve much. They do not belong to intellectuals, because they value luck over intelligence and hard work. "Smart people", on the contrary, always solve their problems. They can often be found behind solutions to seemingly hopeless situations. Intellectuals analyze everything around them, apply their knowledge to overcome any obstacles. As a result, all people can be divided into those who dream of winning the lottery and those who only believe in themselves and earn millions.

8. They don't lose their temper. Researchers tested self-control. These are signs of intelligence - only a smart person can control his momentary desires for more in the future. Unfortunately, many people cannot wait for experimental results and rely on hasty conclusions.

9. They have developed intuition. Intellectuals have a very developed intuition. That doesn't mean they have any superpowers. They only understand the feelings and actions of others very well. Such individuals quickly sense whether a person needs to talk to someone or when his mood suddenly changes, for example, after a phone call. This quality makes "wise people" excellent friends who are able to support, listen and give good advice in solving any problem. Even if the intellectuals notice the change in your behavior, even if they do not admit it to you.

10. They only take risks they can bear. Have you ever heard of people who blow all their money gambling? They don't know how to assess risks, so you can't call them smart. Taking risks is a good thing, and those who never take risks lead incredibly boring lives. At the same time, intelligent people take the time to look for and assess the risk before taking action. Despite the fact that none of the once successful businessmen went bankrupt, they quickly rose and proved that their work was worth it. If a wise man fails, he will rise again, and in the end his perseverance will lead him to victory.

11. They are humble. Believe it or not, pride always precedes failure, and smart people know this very well. If a person has high self-esteem, he will take a seat in the first row and not at the very end, because someone else has already taken the first place. Humility isn't about letting others beat you to the punch, it's about knowing you don't have to prove your worth to anyone. Therefore, you know very well who you are. Humility is an indisputable characteristic of an intellectual.

12. They like to be alone. This does not mean that all extroverts and alcoholics are less intelligent. It's just that intellectuals enjoy their private time and spend it usefully. Admit it, it's hard to be surrounded by people who don't inspire you to be better every day. Intelligence, on the other hand, involves constant self-improvement. Most of the scientists who presented their inventions to the world conceived, developed and implemented their ideas while in the solitary workplace.

13. They are curious. Are you bothered by children who ask too many questions about everything around them? But some of these children grow into curious adults who want to know more about the things we are all familiar with. You should know something about such people - they are very intelligent. And despite the saying that "curious Barbara's nose was cut off", all our

technological advances and other great achievements have only been to ask questions and it was done by those who dared to find answers to them.

14. They don't get along with other people Disagreements between people often stem from misunderstandings, and this is especially evident when it comes to a conversation between a very smart person and a not-so-smart person. Intellectuals look at everything from a special point of view. For the same reason, they tend to question the usual things that others follow too much. As a result, their questions may offend conservative thinkers. Know that if your friend often fights with other people, it is not necessarily because of his stubbornness. To them, he may seem very intelligent.

If we look at history, in fact, Abu Rayhan Beruni, who worked extensively at Khorezm Ma'mun Academy, a scientific school that left a deep mark on the intellectual history of mankind, is one of the great geniuses of mankind. According to historical sources, the great encyclopedist wrote more than 150 works. Only 31 of them have reached us. As the head of our state noted, "Beruni was one of the first in the science of the outer world to propose unique new ideas regarding the theory of the seas and the creation of a spherical globe of the Earth, calculated the radius of the Earth, explained the state of vacuum, that is, the void gave, 500 years before the voyage of Columbus put forward the view of the existence of a continent behind the Pacific and Atlantic oceans, developed the theory of the classification of minerals and their occurrence, founded the science of geodesy. That is why it is not for nothing that the 11th century is called the "Beruni century" by historians of natural sciences all over the world.

The great medieval scientist Abu Raikhan Muhammad ibn Ahmad al-Biruni studied a number of sciences in depth: astronomy, physics, mathematics, geodesy, geology, meteorology, history, etc. He was born in Kot, the ancient capital of Khorezm, and his interest in science grew from a young age. Beruni later studied under the famous scholar Abu Nasr Mansur ibn Iraq. Ibn Iroq wrote a number of works on astronomy, geometry and mathematics, 12 of which he dedicated to Beruni. In addition to his mother tongue, Beruni learned several other languages: Arabic, Sogdian, Persian, Syriac, Greek and ancient Oriya, and later Sanskrit in India.

After compiling the list of his works, Beruni wrote 2 more important books. One of them is Mineralogy. This treatise is considered to be the best, equal work in the field of mineralogy of Central Asia and the Middle East, even in Europe.

According to the information of Beruni's student Abul Fadl al-Serakhat, he died on December 11, 1047. Beruni left a great scientific heritage to the last generations. We know that Beruni had more than 160 translations, works of various sizes, and correspondence related to various fields of science of his time.

The manuscript of Beruni's last work, "The Book of Medicinal Plants", was found in Turkey in the 30s of the 20th century. The work is known as "Saidona".

In his work "India", Beruni analyzed the differences between the customs of Muslims and Indians and put forward the opinion that they depend on the geographical conditions.

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